

The Reality of Applying Leadership Standard in Palestinian Universities According to the International Quality Models

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Abstract: The study aimed to identify the reality of applying the leadership standard according to the international quality models in the Palestinian universities. The study used the analytical descriptive method. The study was conducted on university leadership in Al-Azhar and Islamic universities. The study population consisted of 282 individuals. 119 of them responded, and the questionnaire was used for data collection.

The results of the study were: a high standard of leadership in the research universities; the results showed that the sub-domains of the leadership standard were in the following order: Leaders develop vision, mission, values and ethics and serve as role models for a culture of excellence. Community, leaders participate personally in the development, application and improvement of the university system constantly, leaders manage the process of organizational change, and finally: supports and motivates leaders working at the university and promote a culture of excellence.

The study presented a number of recommendations, the most important of which is: Increasing the interest of the universities in qualifying the university leadership and raising awareness of international quality standards. The adoption of international quality standards as a basis for achieving excellence and creativity. And motivating the university leaders to adopt the approach of excellence and quality in their work.

Keywords: Leadership, International Models of Quality, Palestinian Universities, Al-Azhar University, Islamic University, Palestine.

1. INTRODUCTION

Organizations have become aware of the importance of quality management, excellence and its role as a systematic and systematic activity in reaching products, markets, and operations technology, and new methods that have a competitive edge to cope with others. Quality, excellence and innovation become the most important activity in advanced organizations. Growth, the only activity that belongs to the future, creates wealth, and organizations are increasingly transformed into a new style that can be described as organizations of excellence and innovation (Abu Naser et al., 2016), (Abu Amuna et al., 2016), (Al Shobaki et al., 2016), (El Talla et al., 2017), (Abu Naser et al., 2017), (Al Shobaki et al., 2017), (El Talla et al., 2018), (Abu Naser et al., 2018), (Al Shobaki et al., 2018).

In order for these organizations to achieve the desired distinction, there must be conscious leadership that supports this approach on a sound basis and provides the requirements for achieving a strategic vision, supporting and motivating employees and their participation in decision making, communication with society and social responsibility (Al Shobaki et al., 2016), (El Talla et al., 2017), (Abu Naser et al., 2017), (Al Shobaki et al., 2017), (El Talla et al., 2018), (Abu Naser et al., 2018), (Al Shobaki et al., 2018).

On the other hand, the Arab universities face double challenges compared to the technical gap in various fields, which separate them from the organizations of the developed

world, in addition to facing fierce competition in all fields. The concept of quality and excellence became the only level of performance acceptable in the era of competitiveness, globalization and knowledge, Information, the age of the rule of the human mind and the control of the power of science and human thought. And the fact that the possession of quality and excellence and activation is the way for the survival of institutions and continuity in today's world, and this is only with the presence of university leaders able to lead these universities towards excellence and provide the necessary support and resources to achieve this excellence.

The current study is considered one of the rare studies aimed at answering the following main question: **What is the reality of adopting the standard of leadership according to quality models in Palestinian universities?**

2. RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

In line with the study's questions, the current study seeks to achieve a set of objectives, namely:

1. Identify the availability of leadership standards in international quality models in Palestinian universities.
2. Make recommendations to the university administration to improve the application of quality standards

3. RESEARCH IMPORTANCE

1. To provide university management with information on the level of application of the leadership standard in universities.
2. Drawing the attention of the university administration to the importance of applying international quality models.
3. This study may contribute to drawing the attention of researchers to undertake many studies and researches in modern administrative curricula and apply them to vital sectors such as the higher education sector.

4. RESEARCH LIMITS AND SCOPE

- **The objective limit:** The study was limited to recognizing the reality of Palestinian universities adopting the leadership standard according to the quality models.
- **Spatial Limit:** The application of the study was limited to the Palestinian public universities operating in the southern governorates (Islamic University, Al-Azhar University).
- **Human Limit:** This study focused on the employees of the supervisory posts of the universities in question.

5. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Leadership Standard: (EFQM):

The Leadership standard is the primary driver and leader in all models of quality and international excellence. All models of quality and international excellence start with the Leadership standard. Supporting the top leadership is one of the fundamental pillars of TQM. Without them it will be difficult if not impossible to achieve quality and excellence in performance. This criterion is how the leader creates, supports, and implements a culture of excellence through his actions and behavior.

(Jad Al-Rab, 2010), points out that university leadership in the top management of the university is the one who takes the strategic decisions, plans and policies, which is the main determinant of the efficiency of university performance.

This criterion consists of the following sub-criteria:

- Leaders develop vision, mission, values and ethics and serve as role models for a culture of excellence.
- The participation of leaders personally in the development, application and improvement of the university system constantly.
- Participation and interaction of leaders with beneficiaries, partners and community representatives.
- Supporting and motivating leaders for university employees and promoting a culture of excellence.
- Leading organizational change.

Lassiter (2014) identified a range of things leaders must have to achieve performance excellence:

- **Stability Purpose:** Develop and strengthen vision, values, and trends constantly, and never lose focus on what is important.

- **Leadership is an example:** they are part of the process of improvement, and they represent a model for the conduct and values of the organization.
- **Maintaining high integrity:** They view integrity and ethics as non-negotiable requirements for doing business both inside and outside the organization, where they promote ethical practices and hold accountable immoral behavior.
- **Build and strengthen relationships:** They recognize the importance of building and strengthening relationships with the workforce, beneficiaries, partners, and have a long-term view of stakeholder decisions.
- **Engaging, empowering and gaining employee confidence:** Employees are the backbone of the organization, employees manage and improve processes, they drive and build relationships with beneficiaries, and they find values for the organization and stakeholders.
- **Ask good questions and listen to answer:** they have excellent communication ability, constantly promote the vision, values and trends, also listen to employees, beneficiaries, and the labor market.
- **Making excellence a priority:** where not indulge with poor performance, but promote continuous improvement, performance excellence.
- **Not making perfect enemies of success:** Leaders encourage innovation; smart risk, action, and momentum come through: trying new things, failing, learning, and then refining, improving and trying new things.

6. METHODOLOGY OF THE STUDY:

Study Approach: The study followed the descriptive analytical method, in which it attempts to describe the phenomenon of the subject of the study, analyze its data, and explain the relationship between its components, the opinions that are raised around it, the processes it contains, and the effects that it causes.

The Study Population: The study population is composed of all employees of the supervising posts in the public universities operating in Gaza Strip (Islamic University, Al-Azhar University), which are (282) employees.

The study followed the descriptive analytical method, in which it attempts to describe the phenomenon of the subject of the study, analyze its data, and explain the relationship between its components, the opinions that are raised around it, the processes it contains, and the effects that it causes.

Study Society: The study population consists of all employees of supervisory centers in the public universities operating in Gaza Strip (Islamic University, Al-Azhar University), which number (282) employees.

The Study Sample: The sample of the study was selected using the method of class randomization as one of the

statistical methods used to be representative of the study society according to the rules of scientific research in the selection of samples. The sample size was (135) individuals (47.9%) of the size of the society. The questionnaires were distributed manually, (119) were recovered with (88.1%). A survey sample of 25 individuals was selected from within the study sample. The statistical analysis was conducted to verify the validity and stability of the questionnaire.

Study Tool: To achieve the objective of the study, the questionnaire was used as a data collection tool, developed and developed using the criteria set by the researchers, and to arrive at the questionnaire in its final form. (3) paragraphs, and the area of "the leaders participate personally in the

Table 1: the degrees of the five - dimensional Likert scale

Response	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Not Agree	Strongly Disagree
Class	5	4	3	2	1

In addition, a numerical scale was used to give the mean of the arithmetical mean using the ordinal scale of significance. The study adopted the criterion mentioned by Abdel-Fattah

development, application and improvement of the university system continuously" and be of (3) paragraphs, the area of "participating and interacting leaders with beneficiaries, partners and representatives of society" may be of (3) paragraphs, "Supports and motivates working leaders (3) paragraphs, in addition to the field of "Managing the Leaders of Organizational Change Process" which consists of (4) paragraphs.

Correction Tool Study: The five-point Likert five-point scale was used to determine the importance of each paragraph of the questionnaire to measure respondents' responses to the questionnaire sections as follows:

(2008) to judge the trend when using the five-dimensional Likert scale.

The following table (2) illustrates this:

Table 2: Levels of approval of the sections of the study and its dimensions and axes

SMA	1 – 1.79	1.80 – 2.59	2.60 – 3.39	3.40 – 4.19	4.20 - 5
Degree of Approval	Very Small	Small	Medium	Large	Very Large

7. STATISTICAL PROCESSES:

The study used the Statistical Package of Social Sciences (SPSS) to perform the necessary analysis of the questionnaire data. The following statistical methods and tests were used: percentages, frequencies and arithmetic mean, Pearson Correlation Coefficient to measure the degree of correlation: This test examines the relationship between two variables, may be used to calculate the internal consistency and structural integrity of the questionnaire, the Cronbach's Alpha test to determine the consistency of the resolution paragraphs, the Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test (K-S) test: This test is used to determine whether the data follows the distribution T-Test: To determine if the average response

rate has reached the neutral level (60%) or has increased or decreased, and has been used to ascertain the mean of each paragraph of the questionnaire.

Believe The Study Tool: The questionnaire is intended to measure the questions of the questionnaire for which were put to measure, and two methods were used to verify the veracity of the questionnaire:

- Internal Consistency:** The internal consistency of the questionnaire paragraphs was computed by calculating the correlation coefficients between each paragraph and the total score of its area as follows:

Table 3: Correlation coefficients and the level of significance for each of the paragraphs of the field with the total score of the field

No.	Item	Pearson Correlation	Sig.
Leaders develop vision, mission, values and ethics and serve as role models for a culture of excellence			
1.	The vision and mission of the university are developed to be understood by stakeholders	0.924	0.000
2.	Values, ethics and composition are developed, applied to all levels of leadership	0.942	0.000
3.	The university administration is personally and efficiently involved in the improvement activities within and outside the university	0.879	0.000
Leaders participate personally in the development, application and improvement of the university system			
1.	The University administration supports the University's structure to deliver its policy and strategy	0.826	0.000
2.	The administration of the University develops and implements the University's Operations Management System	0.910	0.000
3.	The evolution of the University administration implements processes:	0.715	0.000

No.	Item	Pearson Correlation	Sig.
	measurement, optimization and a balanced set of results		
The leaders share and interact with beneficiaries, partners and community representatives			
1.	The University administration meets, understands and responds to the needs, expectations and expectations of students, staff and stakeholders	0.860	0.000
2.	Management encourages: individuals, teams, and stakeholder groups for their contribution and loyalty	0.921	0.000
3.	The Department engages and interacts with the activities of the University, especially conferences and workshops that promote and support excellence	0.847	0.000
Supports and motivates leaders working at the university and promotes a culture of excellence			
1.	The administration of the university will listen effectively and respond with inspiration to the employees at all levels of management	0.859	0.000
2.	Encourages the university administration and helps employees achieve their plans and goals	0.933	0.000
3.	The University administration appreciates the efforts of individuals and teams at all levels in the appropriate manner	0.920	0.000
Leaders manage organizational change			
1.	The management of the university understands the motives for internal and external change, its impact and its justifications	0.884	0.000
2.	The University administration understands and supports the changes required in the organizational framework of the University	0.907	0.000
3.	The University administration provides resources and investments that support the process of change	0.911	0.000
4.	The University administration analyzes and manages the risks associated with the process of change and effective implementation	0.935	0.000

It is clear from the previous table that the first area "develops leaders' vision, mission, values and ethics and is an example of a culture of excellence" is directly linked to all the paragraphs that measure it. The correlation coefficients ranged from 0.879 to 0.942. The system of the university continuously "is directly correlated with all the paragraphs it measures. The correlation coefficients ranged from 0.715 to 0.910. The third area," the leaders share and interact with beneficiaries, partners and community representatives "is directly linked to all the paragraphs that measure it. (0.847 - 0.9 21). The fourth area "supports and stimulates leaders working at the university and promotes a culture of excellence" is directly linked to all the paragraphs it measures. The correlation coefficients ranged from 0.859 to

0.933. The fifth and final area "leaders direct the process of organizational change" (0.884 - 0.935), all of which are statistically significant at ($\alpha = 0.01$), and indicate the correlation of the paragraphs that measure the first field in their area, which means that they are internally consistent with the field you measure which is a key for measuring it.

2. **Structural Honesty:** Structural honesty is one measure of tool reliability, which shows how closely each area of study relates to the overall score of the questionnaire. The results show that the correlation coefficients ranged between (0.883 - 0.969) and thus the scale is very high.

Table 4: correlation coefficients and level of significance for each field and the total score of the questionnaire

No.	Dimension	Pearson Correlation	Sig.
1.	Leaders develop vision, mission, values and ethics and serve as role models for a culture of excellence	0.874	0.000
2.	Leaders participate personally in the development, application and improvement of the university system	0.913	0.000
3.	The leaders share and interact with beneficiaries, partners and community representatives	0.914	0.000
4.	Supports and motivates leaders working at the university and promotes a culture of excellence	0.883	0.000

No.	Dimension	Pearson Correlation	Sig.
5.	Leaders manage organizational change	0.969	0.000

Stability of the study instrument:

The persistence of the study questionnaire was determined by the Cronbach's Alpha Coefficient. It is clear from the following table that the value of the Cronbach coefficient

was high for all domains, ranging from 0.748 to 0.924. The Cronbach's Alpha Coefficient (0.965), which means that the questionnaire has high stability.

Table 5: Determination of the stability of the resolution using Cronbach's Alpha

No.	Dimension	No. Of Items	Cronbach's Alpha
1.	Leaders develop vision, mission, values and ethics and serve as role models for a culture of excellence	3	0.902
2.	Leaders participate personally in the development, application and improvement of the university system	3	0.748
3.	The leaders share and interact with beneficiaries, partners and community representatives	3	0.850
4.	Supports and motivates leaders working at the university and promotes a culture of excellence	3	0.885
5.	Leaders manage organizational change	4	0.924
Standard Leadership as a whole		16	0.965

Answer the study questions:

In order to answer the study question, the researchers used several statistical methods, such as: arithmetical averages, standard deviations, as well as the use of a single sample test for each of the domains. The answer of the paragraph is positive in the sense that the sample agrees with its content if the calculated t value is greater than the tabular t value of 1.99 or the probability value is less than 0.05 and the arithmetic mean of the paragraph is greater than (3), the paragraph is negative in the sense that the sample do not agree with their content if the calculated t value is less than the t-value of the t-table, which is 1.99, the probability value is greater than 0.05, the arithmetic mean of the paragraph is smaller than (3). The views of the sample in the paragraph are neutral (moderately agreeable) if the probability value is greater than (0.05).

In reviewing the responses of the sample of the study on the extent to which the leadership criterion was adopted, Table 6 indicates that the mathematical averages of all areas of the field "develop the leaders' vision, mission, values and ethics and serve as role models for the culture of excellence" ranged from 3.84 to 3.97. In general, this field obtained an arithmetic mean (3.89), and the second area, "Leaders

participate personally in the development, application and improvement of the university system continuously". The mathematical averages ranged from (3.68 to 3.89). In general, the field obtained an arithmetic mean (3.77). The third area "Leaders and leaders interact and interact with beneficiaries, partners and community representatives". The mathematical averages ranged from (3.88 - 4.14). In general, this field obtained an arithmetic average (3.83). The fourth area "supports and motivates the leaders of the university and enhances the culture of excellence." The mathematical averages ranged from 3.50 to 3.65, in general, the field has an average of (3.55). In the fifth and final field, "leaders lead the process of organizational change", the averages ranged between (3.49 - 3.72). In general, the questionnaire as a whole has obtained an average of (3.72), which is a large degree. The researchers attribute this to the awareness of the university leaders and their interest in applying sound foundations in management. Most of the university leaders are veteran academics that have considerable experience in administrative work and scientific knowledge and resulting from their qualifications.

Table 6: Analysis of paragraphs and areas of leadership

No.	Item / Dimension	Mean	S. D.	T – Test	Sig.	Rank
1.	The vision and mission of the university are developed to be understood by stakeholders	3.97	0.64	16.26	0.00	1
2.	Values, ethics and composition are developed, applied to all levels of leadership	3.84	0.75	12.02	0.00	3
3.	The university administration is personally and efficiently involved in the improvement activities within and outside the	3.87	0.81	11.79	0.00	2

No.	Item / Dimension	Mean	S. D.	T – Test	Sig.	Rank
	university					
Leaders develop vision, mission, values and ethics and serve as role models for a culture of excellence		3.89	0.62	15.61	0.00	-
1.	The University administration supports the University's structure to deliver its policy and strategy	3.89	0.79	12.19	0.00	1
2.	The administration of the University develops and implements the University's Operations Management System	3.74	0.74	10.76	0.00	2
3.	The evolution of the University administration implements processes: measurement, optimization and a balanced set of results	3.68	0.83	8.91	0.00	3
Leaders participate personally in the development, application and improvement of the university system		3.77	0.65	13.00	0.00	-
1.	The University administration meets, understands and responds to the needs, expectations and expectations of students, staff and stakeholders	3.77	0.76	11.08	0.00	2
2.	Management encourages: individuals, teams, and stakeholder groups for their contribution and loyalty	3.58	0.83	7.53	0.00	3
3.	The Department engages and interacts with the activities of the University, especially conferences and workshops that promote and support excellence	4.14	0.70	17.70	0.00	1
The leaders share and interact with beneficiaries, partners and community representatives		3.83	0.58	15.71	0.00	-
1.	The administration of the university will listen effectively and respond with inspiration to the employees at all levels of management	3.51	0.80	6.98	0.00	2
2.	Encourages the university administration and helps employees achieve their plans and goals	3.50	0.79	6.96	0.00	3
3.	The University administration appreciates the efforts of individuals and teams at all levels in the appropriate manner	3.65	0.83	8.51	0.00	1
Supports and motivates leaders working at the university and promotes a culture of excellence		3.55	0.69	8.76	0.00	-
1.	The management of the university understands the motives for internal and external change, its impact and its justifications	3.72	0.76	10.40	0.00	1
2.	The University administration understands and supports the changes required in the organizational framework of the University	3.68	0.77	9.42	0.00	2
3.	The University administration provides resources and investments that support the process of change	3.51	0.82	6.80	0.00	3
4.	The University administration analyzes and manages the risks associated with the process of change and effective implementation	3.49	0.86	6.17	0.00	4
Leaders manage organizational change		3.60	0.67	9.78	0.00	-
Standard Leadership as a whole		3.72	0.55	14.28	0.00	-

The results indicate that the responses of the members of the research sample exceeded the average approval level, which is 3 in all the paragraphs. The low dispersion is also evident, which indicates the convergence of their views. Given the probabilistic value (SIG), there were no differences in the views of the study sample members on the "availability of

regulatory requirements" clauses. All of the paragraphs were statistically significant at the level of ($\alpha \leq 0.01$).

The following table illustrates the analysis of sub-areas of the Leadership standard:

Table 7: Analysis of the domains of the Leadership standard

No.	Dimension	Mean	S. D.	T – Test	Sig.	Rank
1.	Leaders develop vision, mission, values and ethics and serve as role models for a culture of excellence	3.89	0.62	15.61	0.00	1
2.	Leaders participate personally in the development, application and improvement of the university system	3.77	0.65	13.00	0.00	3
3.	The leaders share and interact with beneficiaries, partners and community representatives	3.83	0.58	15.71	0.00	2
4.	Supports and motivates leaders working at the university and promotes a culture of excellence	3.55	0.69	8.76	0.00	5
5.	Leaders manage organizational change	3.60	0.67	9.78	0.00	4
Standard Leadership as a whole		3.72	0.55	14.28	0.00	-

In general, the adoption of the Leadership standard obtained an average of (3.72), a large degree, and the standard deviation of (0.55), which means that the dispersion is low, indicating the convergence of their views. The order of the fields is as follows: "Leaders develop vision, mission, values and ethics and set an example for a culture" in the first order with an arithmetical average (3.89), the field "Leaders and leaders interact with beneficiaries, partners and community representatives" in the second order with an average of 3.83, while the area of "leaders participate personally in the development, application and improvement of the university system constantly" has obtained the third order with an average arithmetic (3.77), while the field of "leaders lead the process of organizational change" was ranked fourth with an average of (3.60), while the field "supports and motivates the leaders of the university and promotes the culture of excellence", it obtained the fifth and final ranking with an arithmetic mean (3.55).

Previous results show that university leaders manage their universities well in line with quality and excellence.

The results were consistent with the studies of Al-Masri (2014), (Al-Masri, Badri and Selim, 2006), (Al-Dajani, 2011), (Abu Saada, 2013), which indicated a high degree of leadership standard.

The results differed with the studies of Al-Samadi (2009), Zubair (2010) and Al-Jabaree (2009), which indicated a moderate degree of leadership standard.

The researchers believe that Leadership is the starting point for quality and excellence. The leadership of this approach helps universities move forward towards excellence. This is confirmed by the results of a study (Balzer, 2015) that states the need to improve leadership awareness and understanding and support for institutions of higher education agile. Therefore, the university departments and their leaders should be the first building blocks to build a distinguished university. It is a good role model for employees. It has a clear and strong strategy in this direction. It also has the human and material resources to support and build the culture of excellence

8. RESULTS

The study reached a number of results:

- There is a high degree of application of the leadership standard in Palestinian public universities.
- Leaders are involved in the development, implementation and improvement of the university system continuously; leaders manage organizational change; and finally, they support and motivate leaders. Working at the university and promoting a culture of excellence.

9. RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the above results, the study recommended:

- Increasing the interest of universities in qualifying university leadership and raising awareness of international quality standards.
- Adopting the application of international quality standards as a basis for achieving excellence and creativity.
- To motivate university leaders to adopt the approach of excellence and quality in their work.

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